

Best Practice Guide: Designing Circular Biomethane Markets in Industrial Agriculture

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Context and Motivation

Ireland's dairy sector faces dual environmental and economic pressures: reducing emissions and nutrient pollution while sustaining production. Biorefining technologies—especially anaerobic digestion (AD) to produce biomethane and nutrient-rich digestate—offer a promising solution. Yet successful uptake requires more than technical viability. This best practice guide synthesises findings from a three-round modified Delphi study involving 61 stakeholders from dairy processing, finance, academia and public policy, identifying the structural enablers of a functional circular biomethane market.

1. Clarify circular objectives

Avoid narrow energy framing. Biomethane strategies must go beyond decarbonisation to actively support nutrient recovery, soil health and water protection.

Despite Ireland's potentially strong feedstock availability, vested interests across agriculture, energy and land-use sectors can hinder alignment. Coordinated action is needed to ensure these interests are reconciled—so that circular objectives are not undermined by siloed incentives or short-term priorities.

Digestate is not a waste by-product—it is central to nutrient circularity and must be regulated, valued and reintegrated safely.

2. Coordinate infrastructure with market design

Strategically plan AD plant locations using spatial analysis to reduce feedstock competition and prevent stranded assets. Develop standardised and modular AD technologies to lower costs, improve replicability and build investor confidence. Support regional supply chains through comprehensive feedstock databases and monitoring systems.

3. Reform rules and align incentives

Reclassify digestate as a co-product or by-product, not waste, to unlock market potential and reduce regulatory burdens. Harmonise national and EU regulations; adopt end-of-waste criteria and ensure alignment with CSRD and taxonomy rules. Clarify carbon accounting rules so agricultural actors receive recognition for emissions reductions linked to feedstock provision.

4. Empower farmers through cooperative models

Foster cooperative ownership structures to ensure farmer participation and long-term feedstock security. Explore inclusive financial instruments (e.g. MilkFlex-style loans) to derisk investment and link repayment to output flows or prices.

5. Support market activation for all outputs

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Establish price guarantees and purchase obligations for digestate and bio-based fertilisers to create stable demand. Promote eco-labelling, consumer awareness and independent product validation to build trust in circular products.

6. Enable social buy-in and cross-sectoral governance

Engage local communities early and transparently; develop social impact assessments and benefit-sharing mechanisms. Integrate land, water and fertiliser policies into biomethane strategies to avoid siloed approaches and unintended environmental trade-offs or consequences.

Key takeaway

Scaling biomethane in dairy-intensive systems requires more than subsidies or technology trials. A truly circular strategy must redesign market rules, infrastructure and governance to align environmental goals with financial and operational realities. Ireland can become a model for sustainable agri-bioeconomy transitions— if it ensures digestate valorisation, supports inclusive financing and puts circularity at the heart of policy design.

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